

Hetero-Ring Formations with Thiocarbohydrazide. Part IV. Reactions of 1-Phenylthiocarbohydrazide.

BY PRAPHULLA CHANDRA GUHA AND SATYENDRA KUMAR
ROY-CHOUDHURY.

In Part III the preparation of 1-phenylthiocarbohydrazide and its behaviour towards aldehydes and ketones, *o*-diketones and their monoximes, halogenated ketones and esters, β -ketoic esters and 1:4-diketones have been described (see preceding paper). In the present part, the action of acids, acid chlorides, acid anhydrides, mustard oils and isocyanates upon 1-phenylthio-carbohydrazide as also the action of chlorides of dibasic acids upon aldehyde-1-phenylthiocarbohydrazones and different ring-closing agents upon mustard oil and isocyanate derivatives of the thiocarbo-hydrazide are to be described.

Formic acid reacts with 1-phenylthiocarbohydrazide to yield 2-phenylhydrazino-1:3:4-thiodiazole, thus:

The presence of the sulphur atom in the ring is proved by its stability towards mercuric oxide treatment: moreover, the insolubility of this substance in alkali proves the absence of any thiol group in this compound. With acetic anhydride, the thio compound does not yield any closed-ring compound as in the case of the reaction with formic acid but, simply the mono-acetyl derivative (II) is formed.

Potassium ethyl-xanthate yields 2-phenylhydrazino-5-thiol-1:3:4-thiodiazole and this reaction is quite similar to the reactions studied by Guha (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, **44**, 1510) with thiosemicarbazides and by Guha and De (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **125**, 1215) with carbo- and thiocarbo-hydrazide.

The action of six different acid chlorides, *viz.* acetyl chloride, benzoyl chloride, carbonyl chloride, phthalyl chloride, malonylchloride and thionyl chloride has been studied with the result that with the first three reagents, 1-phenylthiocarbohydrazide is only converted into its hydrochloride; with the last three however, there were obtained 2-phenylhydrazino-5-hydroxy-6:7-benzo-8-keto-1:3:4-octathiodiazine, 2-phenylhydrazino-5-hydroxy-6:7-dihydro-7-keto-1:3:4-thioheptadiazine and 2-phenylhydrazino-5-sulphoxy-1:5:3:4-dithiobiazole respectively, thus:

Though phosgene was found to be of little use for the formation of heterocyclic compounds by reacting directly with 1-phenylthiocarbohydrazide, it has however been possible to make it react with benzal and *p*-nitro-benzal derivatives of the hydrazide to yield thiodiazole derivatives, thus:

The formation of these closed-ring compounds is solely due to the fact that in its benzal- and *p*-nitrobenzal- derivatives the hydrazide has lost much of its basic character and it can no longer form any hydrochloride, which if once formed, as in the case of the free 1-phenylthiocarbonylhydrazide, does not show any tendency whatsoever to react further with acid chlorides.

Mono-substituted thiocarbonylhydrazides react with carbimides and thiocarbimides to form the corresponding carbophenylamides and carbothiophenylamides (*cf.* Guha and De, *loc. cit.*).

The ring-closure of this type of lengthened chain-compounds has been effected with strong hydrochloric acid, potassium hydroxide solution and ferric chloride. Phenylthiocarbonylhydrazide-carbophenyl amide (PhNH·NH·CS·NH·NH·CO·NHPH) loses one molecule of sulphuretted hydrogen and yields 1-phenyl-2-phenylhydrazino-5-keto-4 : 5-dihydro-1 : 3 : 4-triazole on being boiled with 20 per cent. potassium hydroxide solution, thus :

Arndt and Bielich (*Ber.*, 1922, 55, 341) analogously obtained anilino-urazole from the hydrazide, PhNH·CS·NH·NH·CO·NH₂ and phenylthiourazole and thiourazole from the hydrazide PhNH·CO·NH·NH·CS·NHPH on treatment with sodium hydroxide solution,

Potassium hydroxide solution brings about the ring-closure of the dicarbothioamide PhNH·NH·CS·NH·NH·CS·NHPH to yield simultaneously two thiobiazole compounds. One is formed by the loss of one molecule of aniline and the other by the elimination of one molecule of sulphuretted hydrogen. The two products, *vis.*, 2-phenylhydrazino-5-anilino-1 : 3 : 4-thiodiazole and 2-phenylhydrazino-5-thiol-1 : 3 : 4-thiodiazole can be separated by taking advantage of the solubility in alkali of the latter by virtue of the thiol group present in it. The thiolthiodiazole readily forms a disulphide and

gives a triacetyl derivative. The thiodiazoles are formed according to the following scheme: --

Arndt and Milde (*Ber.*, 1921, 54, 2089) obtained imino-thiol-triazoles from hydrazides of the type $\text{RNH}\cdot\text{CS}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{CS}\cdot\text{NHR}$ ($\text{R} = \text{Ph}$, or H). It is noticeable that Arndt and Milde's compounds do not contain any sulphur in the ring. Guha and Guha obtained, however, 2-phenylimino-5-thiol-2:3-dihydro-1:3:4-thiodiazole (which contains an atom of sulphur in the ring) from phenylthiosemicarbazide-methyldithiocarboxylate. Evidently the present reaction combines in it both types of ring formation as studied by Arndt and Milde and by Guha and Guha.

Concentrated hydrochloric acid acts upon the carbothiophenylamide ($\text{PhNH}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{CS}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{CS}\cdot\text{NHPh}$) to yield 2:5-diketo-1:3:4-thiodiazole, the formation of which can only be explained on the assumption that in the first stage 2-phenylhydrazino-5-phenylimino-1:3:4-thiodiazole is formed which yields the diketo-thiodiazole on hydrolysis, thus:—

(cf. Freund and Imgart, *Ber.*, 1895, 28, 949; Busch, Lotz and Schmidt, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1914, 90, 57; *Ber.*, 1913, 46, 2240; Guha, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 44, 1502).

Two molecules of phenylthiocarbohydrazide-carbophenylamide lose two atoms of hydrogen by the oxidising action of ferric chloride to yield a disulphide of the composition $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2\text{N}_{10}\text{S}_2$:

Hydrazine hydrate has been shown (Part III) to react with methyl-phenyldithiocarbazine to yield methyl-phenylthiocarbohydrazide. It was expected that like hydrazine hydrate, ethylene and phenylenediamines might also react with the carbazine to give open-chain compounds $C_6H_5(NH.CS.NH.NHPh)$, or $C_6H_5(NH.CS.NH.NHPh)_2$. But, peculiarly enough, methyl-phenyl-dithiocarbazine has been found to react with the above diamines to yield different types of hetero-cyclic compounds. With ethylenediamine it gives 2-anilnamino-2:3:4:5-tetrahydro-1:3-thiazole,

and with *o*-phenylene-diamine it gives 1-phenyl-2:3-benzo-5-thiol-1:4:5-triazine, thus:

The benzo-thiol-triazine is readily soluble in alkali and forms a disulphide and a monoacetyl derivative. A similar thiol-benzotriazine was prepared by Guha and Ray (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, **2**, 81) by the action of potassium ethyl xanthate upon *o*-aminophenylhydrazine.

EXPERIMENTAL.

2-Phenylhydrazino-1:3:4-thiodiazole (I).—Phenylthiocarbohydrazide (2.5 g.) was heated with 10 c.c. of formic acid (100 per cent.) under reflux on a water-bath for 15 minutes when a clear solution was obtained which on cooling deposited a cake-like substance. It was powdered, washed with water and crystallised from alcohol in white plates, m.p. 220° with decomposition (yield almost quantitative). (Found: S, 16.92. $C_6H_5N_4S$ requires S, 16.69 per cent.). The compound is insoluble in acids and alkalis.

1-Phenyl-5-acetyl-thiocarbohydrazone (II).—Phenylthiocarbohydrazide (2 g.) was covered with a sufficient quantity of acetic

anhydride when a clear solution was obtained with much evolution of heat. After some time, a crystalline precipitate separated out which was crystallised from alcohol in white rectangular plates. It shrinks at 168° and melts with decomposition at 172°-173°. It dissolves in alkali and can be precipitated by acids. (Found: N, 24·82. $C_6H_{11}ON_2S$ requires N, 25·00 per cent.).

On heating phenylthiocarbohydrazide with acetic anhydride and proceeding in the usual way, only a small quantity of the acetyl derivative could be isolated from the reaction mixture which consisted mainly of tarry matters.

Action of Potassium Ethyl xanthate: Formation of 2-Phenylhydrazino-5-thiol-1:3:4-thiodiazole (III).—A mixture of carbon bisulphide (2 g.) and 1-phenylthiocarbohydrazide (3·6 g.) dissolved in 20 c.c. of alcohol (containing 1·5 g. of KOH) was heated in a sealed tube at 100° for five hours. On cooling, crystals of the potassium salt deposited which were dissolved in water and the free acid obtained by acidification with hydrochloric acid. It was purified by dissolving in alkali and reprecipitating with acid. It was crystallised from hydrochloric acid, m.p. 127° with decomposition. (Yield 1 gm.). It tarnishes on exposure to the air. (Found: S, 28·82. $C_6H_8N_2S_2$ requires S, 28·48 per cent.).

The *disulphide* of compound (III) was prepared by boiling it with a solution of ferric chloride for about 15 minutes and crystallising the solid thus obtained from a large quantity of alcohol in red needles, m.p. 237° (with decomposition). (Found: S, 29·12. $C_{10}H_{14}N_2S_2$ requires S, 28·57 per cent.).

Action of Phosgene.—Phenyl-thiocarbohydrazide was suspended in benzene in a stoppered flask and the required quantity of phosgene (in toluene solution) was gradually added. The mixture was shaken for an hour and kept overnight with a loose cork. Next day, it was heated under reflux for a few minutes. The solid product thus separated was proved to be the hydrochloride of the base by preparing the benzaldehyde derivative as also by taking the mixed melting point.

Action of Acetyl Chloride.—The hydrazide was heated with acetyl chloride under reflux for about half an hour when a clear solution was obtained. On concentration a white solid was obtained and was proved to be the hydrochloride of the hydrazide.

Action of Benzoyl Chloride.—On being heated with benzoyl chloride in chloroform solution the thio-compound yielded the same hydrochloride.

2-Phenylhydrazino-5-hydroxy-6:7-benzo-8-keto-1:3:4-octathiodiazine (IV).—A mixture of phthalyl chloride (2 g.) and phenylthiocarbonylhydrazide (1·8 g.) was heated in benzene solution under reflux for ten minutes when a white solid separated which was filtered, washed with benzene and crystallised from acetic acid in white long plates. It assumes a slight reddish tinge at 185° and melts at 206° with decomposition (yield quantitative). It dissolves in alkali and can be precipitated by the addition of acids. (Found: S, 10·71. $C_{11}H_{11}O_2N_4S$ requires S, 10·25 per cent.).

2-Phenylhydrazino-5-hydroxy-7-keto-6:7-dihydro-1:3:4-heptathiodiazine (V).—Malonyl chloride (1·4 g.) was added to a benzene solution of phenylthiocarbonylhydrazide (1·8 g.) when a brown flocculent precipitate was formed which was filtered, washed with benzene and purified by dissolving in alkali and precipitating with acid, and repeating this process for several times; it was insoluble in almost all organic solvents. It melts at 201-202° with decomposition. (Found: N, 21·96. $C_{10}H_{10}O_2N_4S$ requires N, 22·40 per cent.).

2-Phenylhydrazino-5-sulphoxy-1:5:4:3-dithiobiazole (VI).—A benzene solution of thionyl chloride (1·2 g.) and phenylthiocarbonylhydrazide (1·8 g.) were heated under reflux for half an hour when the suspended solid went into solution. On cooling an amorphous solid separated out which was redissolved in benzene and filtered hot. On cooling, an amorphous mass separated again which was washed with alcohol and dried. It melts with decomposition at 220° and is insoluble in all other solvents, acids and alkalis. (Found: S, 28·48. $C_7H_8ON_4S_2$ requires S, 28·07 per cent.).

ACTION OF CHLORIDES OF DIBASIC ACIDS UPON ALDEHYDE-PHENYL THIOCARBOHYDRAZONES.

2-Benzalhydrazone of 4-Phenyl-5-keto-tetrahydro-1:3:4-thiodiazole (VII).—Benzaldehyde-1-phenylthiocarbonylhydrazone (2·7 g.) was suspended in benzene and to it the required quantity of phosgene (20 per cent. in toluene solution) was added. The mixture on being heated for an hour on the water bath gave a clear solution. On cooling, a crystalline precipitate separated out which was recrystallised from benzene in white rectangular plates. It shrinks at 195° and melts at 204-205° (yield 1 gm.). (Found: N, 19·13. $C_{11}H_{11}ON_4S$ requires N, 18·94 per cent.).

2-Nitrobenzalhydrazone of 4-Phenyl-5-keto-tetrahydro-1:3:4-thio-diazole (VIII).—The method of preparation was the same as in the case of the preceding compound. The compound was crystallised from a mixture of alcohol and pyridine in yellow rectangular plates, m. p. 259°. (Found: N, 20·63. $C_{15}H_{11}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 20·52 per cent.).

ACTION OF MUSTARD OILS AND *iso*CYANATES.

Phenylthiocarbohydrazide-carbophenylamide (IX).—Phenylthiocarbohydrazide (1·8 g.) was heated under reflux with phenyl isocyanate (1·2 g.) in alcoholic solution for a minute when an insoluble product separated out. This was washed with methyl alcohol to remove some admixed tarry matters and crystallised from acetic acid in white plates, m. p. 209° (with decomp.). It dissolves in alkali and is precipitated by acids. (Found: N, 23·42. $C_{14}H_{15}ON_2S$ requires N, 23·26 per cent.).

Phenylthiocarbohydrazide-carbothiophenylamide (X).—An alcoholic solution of phenylthiocarbohydrazide (2·7 g.) was heated under reflux with phenyl mustard oil (2·7 g.) for two minutes, and the separated solid was crystallised from a large quantity of alcohol; m. p. 173-174°. It dissolves in alkali and can be precipitated by acids. (Found: N, 21·98. $C_{14}H_{15}N_2S_2$ requires N, 22·08 per cent.).

Phenylmethyl-thiocarbohydrazide-carbothiophenylamide (XI).—An alcoholic suspension of phenyl-methyl-thiocarbohydrazide (0·4 g.) was heated with phenyl mustard oil (0·3 g.) under reflux for one hour and the solid thus obtained was crystallised from dilute pyridine in white plates, m. p. 219-220° with decomp. (Found: N, 21·34. $C_{14}H_{17}N_2S_2$ requires N, 21·14 per cent.).

m-Tolylthiocarbohydrazide-carbothiophenylamide (XII) was similarly prepared as the preceding compound and was crystallised from acetic acid in white rectangular plates, m. p. 160° with decomp. (Found: S, 19·68. $C_{15}H_{17}N_2S_2$ requires S, 19·34 per cent.).

1-Phenyl-2-phenylhydrazino-5-keto-4:5-dihydro-1:3:4-triazole (XIII).—Phenylthiocarbohydrazide-carbophenylamide (7 g.) was heated under reflux with 40 c. c. of 20 per cent. potassium hydroxide solution for half an hour when a solid mixed with a little oily matter separated from the solution. The oily matter was removed by passing steam and the solid was crystallised from dilute alcohol in white needles. It shrinks at 238° and melts at 244-245° (yield 0·5

gm.). It is insoluble in acids and alkalis. (Found: N, 26.12. $C_{14}H_{13}ON_3$ requires N, 26.22 per cent.).

2-Phenylhydrazino-5-anilino-1:3:4-thiodiazole (XIV) and *2-Phenylhydrazino-5-thiol-1:3:4-thiodiazole* (XV).—Phenylthiocarbonyldrazide-carbothiophenylamide (10 g.) was heated with 60 c. c. of 20 per cent. potassium hydroxide solution under reflux for half an hour when a deep black solution containing a red oily substance was obtained. The oil was removed by passing steam and was proved to be aniline. The solution on cooling yielded a fine white crystalline product (XIV) which was crystallised from water after animal charcoal treatment in white rectangular plates. It shrinks at 195° and melts at 199° (yield 1.0 gm.). It is readily soluble in hydrochloric acid. (Found: N, 24.58; S, 11.61. $C_{14}H_{13}N_3S$ requires N, 24.74; S, 11.31 per cent.).

Isolation of Compound (XV).—The mother-liquor was next acidified with hydrochloric acid when a flocculent precipitate appeared which was crystallised from a large quantity of alcohol in shining white plates, m.p. $258-259^\circ$ (yield 2.5 gm.). (Found: N, 25.42; S, 28.93. $C_8H_8N_4S_2$ requires N, 25.00; S, 28.57 per cent.).

The *disulphide* was prepared by heating the thiol compound (XV) with an excess of ferric chloride solution for ten minutes and the separated solid mass was purified by dissolving in acetic acid and precipitating with water. Being insoluble, it could not be crystallised from any organic solvent. It shrinks at 195° and melts with decomposition at 205° . (Found: N, 25.47. $C_{10}H_{14}N_4S_4$ requires N, 25.08 per cent.).

The *triacetyl derivative* was prepared by heating the thiol compound with acetic anhydride for about 15 minutes. On cooling a crystalline product separated out which was washed with water and alcohol and dried, m.p. $206-207^\circ$. It is insoluble in alkali. (Found: N, 16.38. $C_{14}H_{14}O_6N_4S_2$ requires N, 16.00 per cent.).

Action of Hydrochloric Acid upon Phenylthiocarbonyldrazide-carbothiophenylamide: Formation of 2:5-Diketo-tetrahydro-1:3:4-thiodiazole (XVI).—The thio compound (7 g.) on being heated with strong hydrochloric acid for one and a half hours went into solution with separation of sulphur. The filtered solution on neutralisation with sodium carbonate yielded a solid admixed with an oily matter which was removed by passing steam. The solid was crystallised from alcohol in white needles, m.p. 222° . (Found: N, 23.82; S, 27.69. $C_2H_4O_2N_2S$ requires N, 23.73; S, 27.11 per cent.).

Oxidation of Phenylthiocarbonylhydrazidecarboxenylamide with Ferric Chloride: Formation of (XVII).—The thio compound was heated with ferric chloride solution for about half an hour and the separated solid was crystallised from acetic acid in red needles, m.p. 198-199° with decomposition. It is insoluble in acid and alkali. (Found: N, 23·34; S, 11·48. $C_{10}H_8N_2S_2O_2$ requires N, 23·20; S, 11·02 per cent.).

Action of Ferric Chloride upon Phenylthiocarbonylhydrazidecarboxenylamide: Formation of 2-Anilino-5-phenylazo-1:3:4-thio-diazole (XVIII).

The carboxenylamide on being heated with an excess of ferric chloride solution for about half an hour, yielded a red coloured solid. The solid was freed from sulphur by washing with carbon bisulphide and was crystallised from a mixture of alcohol and pyridine in red needles, m.p. 256-257°. It is insoluble in acids and alkalis. (Found: S, 11·72. $C_{14}H_{11}N_3S$ requires S, 11·39 per cent.). This compound was also obtained when compound (XIV) was oxidised with hydrogen peroxide in alcoholic solution.

2-Phenylhydrazino-2:3:4:5-dihydro-1:3-thiazole (XIX).—Methylphenyldithiocarbazine (6 g.) contained in a beaker was covered with a sufficient quantity of ethylene diamine when a violent reaction ensued with considerable evolution of heat. The mixture was then heated on a water-bath for a few minutes to complete the reaction. The separated solid was filtered, washed with alcohol and crystallised from pyridine, m.p. 223° (yield 1·5 gm.) It is insoluble in acids and alkalis. (Found: N, 21·58. $C_9H_{11}N_3S$ requires N, 21·76 per cent.).

1-Phenyl-2:3-benzo-5-thiol-dihydro-1:4:6-triazine (XX).—An intimate mixture of the carbazine (7·2 g.) and *o*-phenylene diamine (4·3 g.) was heated in an oil-bath at 130-140° for three to four hours during which a peculiar pungent smell was emitted. The reaction mixture was cooled, dissolved in potassium hydroxide solution and steam was passed in to remove some tar formed during the reaction. The filtered solution was then neutralised with dilute hydrochloric acid and the white precipitate thus obtained was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 292-293° (yield 1·5 gm.). (Found: N, 17·34. $C_{12}H_{11}N_3S$ requires N, 17·43 per cent.).

The *acetyl derivative* was prepared in the usual manner and was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 203-204°. It dissolves readily in alkali and is precipitated by hydrochloric acid. (Found: N, 15·23. $C_{11}H_{11}ON_3S$ requires N, 14·84 per cent.).

The *disulphide* was prepared by boiling the thiol compound with ferric chloride and the yellow solid thus obtained was washed repeatedly with water and alcohol. It shrinks at 230° and does not melt even at 300°. (Found: S, 13.72. $C_{24}H_{30}N_4S_8$ requires S, 13.93 per cent.).

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CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
THE UNIVERSITY, DACCA.

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